

SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL LEARNING COMPETENCE AND CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT AMONG PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL TEACHERS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19360319>

ABSTRACT

This study aimed to determine the teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management in elementary schools of Bilar, Batuan, Carmen, Sierra-Bullones, and Pilar (BiBaCaSiPi) districts, Bohol Division, in the school year 2025-2026. The study used a quantitative descriptive survey design, incorporating a correlational method. The study involved a total of 350 public elementary school teachers. The study found that the teachers were predominantly female and mid-career, 41-50 years, revealed "Highly Competent" socio-emotional learning across CASEL dimensions (strongest in relationship skills, weakest in self-awareness) and "Very Well-Managed" classroom management (highest in teacher-student communication, lowest in psychological support). No significant associations existed between demographics (sex, age, position, education, experience) and either competence, per regression analysis. Spearman's correlation confirmed a significant positive association between socio-emotional competence and classroom management, with skills such as self-awareness enhancing discipline and relationships. The study concluded that while demographics were not significant factors, teachers' SEL skills significantly impacted their classroom management practices. The proposed action plan recommends targeted professional development programs focused on enhancing self-awareness and psychological support skills to further improve teachers' overall effectiveness and create more supportive learning environments.

Keywords: *Social-emotional learning (SEL); Classroom management; Teacher competence; Elementary education; Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Teachers play a crucial role in shaping learners' academic success, behavior, and overall development. In contemporary education, effective teaching goes beyond content delivery and requires the ability to manage emotions, build positive relationships, and respond appropriately to diverse classroom situations. These abilities are reflected in teachers' socio-emotional learning (SEL) competence, which has become increasingly important in fostering supportive and productive learning environments. Teachers with strong socio-emotional competence are better able to regulate their emotions, demonstrate empathy, and maintain positive interactions, which contribute to an improved classroom climate and student engagement (Morgan et al., 2022).

Socio-emotional learning competence encompasses key domains such as self-awareness, emotional regulation, social awareness, relationship skills, and responsible decision-making. These competencies are essential for effective classroom management, as they enable teachers to establish discipline, organize instruction, and maintain meaningful communication with students. Research has shown that teachers with high socio-emotional competence are better equipped to handle classroom challenges, reduce disruptive behavior, and promote positive student outcomes (Lozano-Pena et al., 2021). In this sense, socio-emotional competence and classroom management are closely interconnected components of effective teaching practice.

Globally, the integration of socio-emotional learning in education has been widely recognized; however, its implementation remains a challenge due to factors such as insufficient training, limited resources, and teacher workload. Studies indicate that teachers often lack adequate preparation in applying socio-emotional strategies, which affects their ability to manage classrooms effectively and support students' emotional development (Dyson et al., 2023). These challenges highlight the need to strengthen teacher competence in socio-emotional learning as part of professional development initiatives.

In the Philippine context, the importance of socio-emotional learning is supported by educational policies that emphasize holistic development among learners. However, its implementation in schools is still evolving and is often constrained by fragmented programs and limited teacher training (King & Gunewardena, 2022). While initiatives such as *Edukasyong Pagpapakatao* and recent mental health policies aim to address learners' socio-emotional needs, teachers continue to face challenges in integrating these competencies into their daily classroom practices. Studies have shown that while the curriculum promotes the development of values and socio-emotional skills, the actual mastery and application of these competencies among educators and learners remain inconsistent (Parojenog & Felisilda, 2022). This underscores the need to examine teachers' socio-emotional learning competence in relation to their classroom management practices, particularly in public elementary schools.

Classroom management remains a fundamental aspect of teaching, as it directly influences student behavior, engagement, and academic performance. Effective

classroom management involves not only maintaining discipline but also organizing lessons, facilitating interaction, strengthening communication, and creating a psychologically safe learning environment. Teachers who are socially and emotionally competent are more likely to create structured, inclusive, and supportive classrooms that promote positive learning experiences (Callorina et al., 2024).

Despite the growing recognition of socio-emotional learning and its relevance to classroom management, there is limited empirical evidence examining the relationship between these variables among public elementary school teachers in local contexts. In the BiBaCaSiPi districts of the Bohol Division, there is a need to explore how teachers' socio-emotional learning competence relates to their classroom management practices, and whether their profiles influence these variables.

Hence, this study was conducted to determine the level of socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management among public elementary school teachers in the BiBaCaSiPi districts, Bohol Division, for the school year 2025–2026. It also aimed to examine the association between teachers' profile and their socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management, as well as the relationship between socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management. The findings of the study will serve as the basis for a proposed action plan to enhance teachers' competencies and improve classroom practices.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management in elementary schools of Bilar, Batuan, Carmen, Sierra-Bullones, and Pilar (BiBaCaSiPi) districts, Bohol Division, in the school year 2025-2026. The findings of the study served as the basis for a proposed action plan.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following sub-problems:

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1 sex;
 - 1.2 age;
 - 1.3 position held;
 - 1.4 highest educational attainment; and
 - 1.5 teaching experience?
2. What is the level of the socio-emotional learning competence of the respondents in terms of:
 - 2.1 self-awareness;
 - 2.2 emotional regulation;
 - 2.3 social awareness;
 - 2.4 relationship skills; and
 - 2.5 decision making?
3. What is the level of classroom management in terms of:
 - 3.1 discipline inside the classroom;

- 3.2 parents' collaboration;
 - 3.3 organization of the lesson;
 - 3.4 interaction during the lesson;
 - 3.5 teacher-student personal communication; and
 - 3.6 psychological?
4. Is there a significant association between the profile of the teacher-respondents and the level of their socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management?
 5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and the level of their classroom management?
 6. Based on the findings, what plan of action can be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a quantitative descriptive survey design, incorporating a correlational method. It aimed to describe teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management in elementary schools. Data was collected using a modified survey questionnaire to obtain specific insights. The study explored relationships between teacher profiles, their socio-emotional competence, and classroom management through correlational research.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the districts of Bilar, Batuan, Carmen, Sierra Bullones, and Pilar, collectively known as BiBaCaSiPi, located in the Third Congressional District of Bohol. These areas consist of public elementary schools situated in predominantly rural communities. The selected districts provide an appropriate setting for the study, as they represent typical public-school environments in which teachers manage classroom dynamics, student behavior, and instructional demands. This context is relevant for examining socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management among public elementary school teachers.

Research Respondents

The respondents of the study were public elementary school teachers from the districts of Bilar, Batuan, Carmen (Districts 1, 2, and 3), Sierra Bullones, and Pilar (BiBaCaSiPi). A total of 350 teachers participated in the study. The respondents were selected using proportional allocation to ensure that each district was represented according to its size within the total population.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a modified survey questionnaire composed of three parts.

Part I gathered the respondents' demographic profile, including sex, age, position held, highest educational attainment, and teaching experience.

Part II measured the teachers' socio-emotional learning competence across five dimensions: self-awareness, emotional regulation, social awareness, relationship skills, and decision-making. This section consisted of 40 items adapted from Caparoso et al. (2024) and was rated using a 4-point scale. The interpretation of scores is as follows: 3.25–4.00 (Highly Competent) (HC), indicating thorough mastery and consistent high-quality performance; 2.50–3.24 (Moderately Competent) (MC), reflecting acceptable performance with minor need for improvement; 1.75–2.49 (Less Competent) (LC), indicating partial mastery with noticeable gaps; and 1.00–1.74 (Not Competent) (NC), reflecting significant deficiencies that hinder effective performance.

Part III assessed classroom management across six dimensions: discipline, parents' collaboration, lesson organization, classroom interaction, teacher-student communication, and psychological aspect. This section included 60 items adapted from Diaz et al. (2018) and utilized a 4-point Likert scale. The scale is interpreted as follows: 3.25–4.00 (Very Well-Managed) (VW), indicating highly organized and consistently effective practices; 2.50–3.24 (Moderately Well-Managed) (MW), reflecting generally reliable performance with minor gaps; 1.75–2.49 (Less Well-Managed) (LW), indicating basic performance with areas needing improvement; and 1.00–1.74 (Not Well-Managed) (NW), reflecting substantial weaknesses requiring intervention.

The instrument underwent content validation and was pilot-tested among 10 teachers in Sevilla District who were not part of the study but had similar characteristics to the respondents.

Research Procedure

Prior to data collection, the researcher secured approval from the School of Advanced Studies and obtained permission from the Schools Division Superintendent, District Supervisors, and School Heads of the BiBaCaSiPi districts. These approvals ensured compliance with institutional and ethical requirements. Upon approval, the researcher personally administered the questionnaires to the selected respondents. The purpose of the study was explained, and informed consent was obtained. Respondents were given sufficient time to complete the instrument, after which the questionnaires were retrieved. The instrument was pilot-tested among 10 teachers from a non-participating district to ensure clarity and reliability. Necessary revisions were made prior to the actual data collection. All collected data were checked, organized, and prepared for analysis. Ethical standards, including confidentiality and voluntary participation, were strictly observed throughout the study.

Data Analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools were used to analyze the data. Percentage was employed to describe the demographic profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of sex, age, position held, highest educational attainment, and teaching experience. The weighted mean was used to determine the level of teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management. The chi-square test of independence was applied to examine the association between respondents' profiles and their levels of socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management. Spearman's rank correlation was utilized to determine the significant relationship between teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management at the 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

This presents, analyzes, and interprets data on the demographic profile of teachers, teachers' socio-emotional learning competence, and classroom management in elementary schools.

Table 1
Profile of the Teacher-Respondents
n = 350

Category	Frequency	Percentage
1.1 Sex		
Male	32	9.12
Female	318	90.90
1.2 Age		
21 – 30 years old	53	15.10
31 – 40 years old	112	32.00
41 – 50 years old	128	36.60
51 – 60 years old	53	15.10
61 years old and above	4	1.10
1.3 Position		
Teacher I	106	30.30
Teacher II	33	9.40
Teacher III	182	52.00
Master Teacher I	20	5.70
Master Teacher II	9	2.60
1.4 Highest Educational Attainment		
Bachelor Degree Holder	47	13.40
With units in Master's Degree	229	65.40
Master's Degree Graduate	49	14.00
With PhD/EdD units	17	4.90
PhD/EdD Graduate	7	2.30
1.5 Experience		
10 years and below	154	44.00
11 – 20 years	128	36.60
21 – 30 years	63	18.00
31 years and above	5	1.40

Table 1 shows that the teaching workforce in the study area is predominantly female, with females comprising the vast majority of the respondents. This pattern reflects the continuing feminization of elementary teaching, where women remain more strongly represented than men. In terms of age, most respondents were in the 31–50 years old bracket, indicating that the teaching force is largely composed of adults in their mature and mid-career years. This suggests a respondent group that is likely to possess both professional stability and substantial classroom exposure. In terms of rank, the largest proportion of respondents held the position of Teacher III, followed by Teacher I, while only a small number occupied Master Teacher positions. This indicates that most respondents were already in the regular teaching ranks but that relatively fewer had advanced to higher instructional leadership positions. Regarding educational attainment, the majority had units in a master’s degree, while only a limited number had completed doctoral degrees. This suggests that most teachers are pursuing graduate education for professional growth, although full completion of advanced degrees remains less common. In terms of teaching experience, the largest group had 10 years and below in service, followed by those with 11–20 years of experience, indicating a mix of early-career and moderately experienced teachers within the sample.

Overall, the profile points to a teaching population that is predominantly female, professionally active, academically upgrading, and composed largely of teachers in the developing to mid-career stages. This composition is relevant to the study because socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management may be shaped by teachers’ career stage, academic preparation, and accumulated classroom experience. The present result is consistent with Sebastian et al. (2022), who reported that elementary teaching in the Philippines remains female-dominated. It is also aligned with Taculog (2024), whose study of public elementary school teachers found that many respondents were female, within the 31–50 years old range, occupying Teacher III positions, and pursuing or holding graduate qualifications.

Table 2.1
Level of the Socio-Emotional Learning Competence of the
Respondents in terms of Self-Awareness
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. am aware of the teaching practices that I need to improve upon and grow professionally.	3.46	HC
2. can effectively implement the teaching processes with the learners during home visitation.	3.37	HC
3. can recognize the limitations of self and how different self-aspects influence my teaching.	3.45	HC
4. understand that my behaviors are influenced by multiple personal factors, such as my experiences, personality, emotions, knowledge base, opinions, and attitudes.	3.48	HC
5. continuously bridge the differences of my students to build strong interpersonal relations and engage them in learning.	3.43	HC
Composite Mean	3.44	Highly Competent

Table 2.1 presents the level of socio-emotional learning competence of the respondents in terms of self-awareness. The composite mean indicates that the teachers are Highly Competent, suggesting a strong capacity to recognize and understand the personal factors that influence their teaching practices.

Among the indicators, the highest mean was obtained by the statement on understanding that one’s behavior is influenced by experiences, emotions, personality, and related factors. This reflects a high level of reflective awareness, which supports adaptive teaching and informed professional decision-making. Such competence enables teachers to regulate their responses and align their practices with the needs of diverse learners.

In contrast, the lowest mean, though still within the Highly Competent range, pertains to the implementation of teaching processes during home visitation. This may indicate that while teachers possess strong internal awareness, its application in non-classroom contexts is comparatively less consistent, possibly due to situational or environmental constraints.

Overall, the findings suggest that teachers demonstrate well-developed self-awareness, which is essential for professional growth, effective classroom interaction, and learner engagement. This supports the view of Li and Qian (2025) that self-awareness enables teachers to recognize their strengths and limitations, thereby improving instructional practices and emotional regulation. In turn, such competence contributes to more responsive teaching and positive learning environments.

Table 2.2
Level of the Socio-Emotional Learning Competence of the Respondents in terms of Emotional Regulation
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. continuously refine my personal goals about how I implement my teaching practices.	3.37	HC
2. effectively use multiple strategies when I have a strong emotional reaction in the classroom.	3.57	HC
3. recognize my own positive and negative emotions in interacting with the students, parents, and colleagues.	3.60	HC
4. understand that perspective differ according to age, gender, social, ethnic, educational, and economic backgrounds.	3.52	HC
5. use positive approach when dealing with the learners and parents and develop an environment that is free from bias and prejudice.	3.54	HC
Composite Mean	3.52	Highly Competent

Table 2.2 presents the level of socio-emotional learning competence of the respondents in terms of emotional regulation. The composite mean of 3.52, interpreted

as Highly Competent, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong capability in managing their emotions across varied professional situations.

All indicators were rated within the Highly Competent range, reflecting consistent proficiency in emotional regulation practices. The highest mean was obtained by the ability to recognize both positive and negative emotions in interactions with students, parents, and colleagues. This suggests that teachers possess strong emotional awareness, enabling them to monitor their responses and maintain constructive interpersonal relationships.

On the other hand, the lowest mean, though still highly competent, was observed in refining personal goals related to teaching practices. This implies that while teachers are effective in regulating emotions, there is relatively less emphasis on continuous reflective goal-setting as part of their emotional regulation process.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers are competent in applying emotional regulation strategies that support classroom management and professional interactions. This competence contributes to maintaining a positive classroom climate and effective collaboration with stakeholders. The result supports the findings of Morgan et al. (2022), who emphasized that emotional regulation among teachers enhances instructional effectiveness, strengthens relationships, and promotes a supportive learning environment through controlled and adaptive emotional responses.

Table 2.3
Level of the Socio-Emotional Learning Competence of the Respondents in terms of Social Awareness
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. understand the perspective of my learners and can pay attention to their emotional cues inside the classroom.	3.51	HC
2. am successful at providing my students with the necessary skills to answer the activities in the school.	3.45	HC
3. encourage and provide learners' opportunities to mention their concerns in the teaching-learning process, verbally or written.	3.45	HC
4. address individual and group commonalities and uniqueness that exist among students and colleagues.	3.53	HC
5. engage in constructive communication with my colleagues and resolve conflicts when they arise.	3.46	HC
Composite Mean	3.48	Highly Competent

Table 2.3 presents the level of socio-emotional learning competence of the respondents in terms of social awareness. The composite mean of 3.48, interpreted as Highly Competent, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong ability to understand learners' perspectives, recognize diversity, and engage in positive interpersonal interactions.

All indicators were rated within the Highly Competent range, reflecting consistent proficiency in social awareness. The highest mean was obtained by the ability to address individual and group commonalities and differences among students and colleagues. This suggests that teachers are capable of fostering inclusive classroom environments and promoting respect for diversity.

Meanwhile, the lowest means, though still within the Highly Competent level, were observed in providing learners with necessary skills for academic tasks and encouraging students to express their concerns. This implies that while teachers are socially aware, there is relatively less emphasis on facilitating student voice and skill development as part of social awareness practices.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers possess a high level of social awareness, which supports positive classroom relationships, effective communication, and conflict resolution. This competence contributes to a more inclusive and responsive learning environment. This finding is consistent with Lozano-Peña et al. (2021), who emphasized that social awareness enables teachers to understand diverse perspectives, respond to emotional cues, and promote inclusive classroom practices that enhance student engagement and well-being.

Table 2.4
Level of the Socio-Emotional Learning Competence of the Respondents in terms of Relationship Skills
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. use appropriate non-verbal communication with students, parents, and colleagues.	3.62	HC
2. value effective collaboration with stakeholders including the students, parents, and colleagues.	3.67	HC
3. develop a socially and friendly learning environment which is characterized by friendly communication, cooperation, and assistance.	3.64	HC
4. clearly communicate behavioral and academic expectations in a manner that addresses the learners' individual needs and strengths.	3.61	HC
5. am comfortable in extending my help to the learners in addressing their challenges in answering class activities.	3.62	HC
Composite Mean	3.63	Highly Competent

Table 2.4 presents the level of socio-emotional learning competence of the respondents in terms of relationship skills. The composite mean of 3.63, interpreted as Highly Competent, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong ability to build and maintain positive relationships with students, parents, and colleagues.

All indicators were rated within the Highly Competent range, reflecting consistent proficiency in interpersonal communication and collaboration. The highest mean was

obtained by valuing effective collaboration with stakeholders, suggesting that teachers recognize the importance of partnership in enhancing learning outcomes and fostering a supportive educational environment.

On the other hand, the lowest mean, though still highly competent, was observed in clearly communicating behavioral and academic expectations based on learners' individual needs and strengths. This implies that while teachers are effective communicators, there is still an opportunity to further strengthen differentiated and personalized communication practices.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers possess a high level of relationship skills, which contributes to positive classroom climate, effective collaboration, and improved student engagement. These competencies are essential in sustaining harmonious school relationships and supporting learners' academic and socio-emotional development. This finding is consistent with Oberle et al. (2020), who affirmed that teachers with strong relationship skills are more capable of establishing supportive environments, promoting collaboration, and enhancing both student achievement and emotional well-being.

Table 2.5
Level of the Socio-Emotional Learning Competence of the Respondents in terms of Decision Making
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. use facts and feelings in making decisions.	3.59	HC
2. predict and explore possible consequences of different actions and choices.	3.53	HC
3. plan multiple ways to accomplish a goal.	3.47	HC
4. consider the individual differences of my students.	3.49	HC
5. balance the learners' well-being and needs when I implement my teaching practices.	3.38	HC
Composite Mean	3.49	Highly Competent

Table 2.5 presents the level of socio-emotional learning competence of the respondents in terms of decision-making. The composite mean of 3.49, interpreted as Highly Competent, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong ability to make informed and balanced decisions in their professional practice.

All indicators were rated within the Highly Competent range, reflecting consistent proficiency in decision-making processes. The highest mean was obtained by the ability to use both facts and feelings in making decisions, suggesting that teachers are capable of integrating rational judgment with emotional awareness in addressing classroom situations.

In contrast, the lowest mean, though still highly competent, was observed in balancing learners' well-being and needs during the implementation of teaching practices. This implies that while teachers demonstrate effective decision-making, there is relatively less emphasis on prioritizing student-centered considerations in certain situations.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers possess a high level of decision-making competence, which supports effective classroom management, ethical judgment, and responsive instructional practices. This competence enables teachers to anticipate outcomes, consider diverse learner needs, and make appropriate professional decisions. This finding is consistent with Rodriguez et al. (2020), who emphasized that decision-making competence in socio-emotional learning allows teachers to integrate cognitive and emotional processes, leading to more effective teaching practices and improved student outcomes.

Table 3.1
Level of Classroom Management in terms of Discipline
Inside the Classroom
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. involve students in establishing rules and procedures.	3.58	VW
2. share with students the reasons behind the approach/es I use.	3.61	VW
3. provide positive reinforcement to students for appropriate behavior.	3.56	VW
4. make students aware of the consequences for misbehavior.	3.58	VW
5. use class time to reflect on appropriate behavior with the students as a group.	3.59	VW
Composite Mean	3.58	Very Well-Managed

Table 3.1 presents the level of classroom management in terms of discipline inside the classroom. The composite mean of 3.58, interpreted as Very Well-Managed, indicates that teachers demonstrate a high level of effectiveness in implementing disciplinary practices and maintaining an orderly learning environment.

All indicators were rated within the Very Well-Managed range, reflecting consistent use of structured and proactive classroom management strategies. The highest mean was obtained by sharing with students the reasons behind the approaches used, suggesting that teachers emphasize clarity and transparency in enforcing rules, which promotes student understanding and cooperation.

On the other hand, the lowest mean, though still very well-managed, was observed in providing positive reinforcement for appropriate behavior. This implies that while teachers effectively maintain discipline, there is relatively less emphasis on reinforcement strategies compared to other practices.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers are highly competent in managing classroom discipline through clear expectations, consistent procedures, and reflective practices. These strategies contribute to a stable and supportive learning environment that minimizes disruptions and promotes student responsibility. This finding is consistent with Carmen et al. (2022), who emphasized that effective classroom discipline establishes structure, promotes accountability, and enhances student engagement by combining clear expectations, consistent consequences, and positive reinforcement.

Table 3.2
Level of Classroom Management in terms of Parents' Collaboration
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. collaborate with parents on assignments behavioral plan.	3.49	VW
2. teach parents activities to do with at home to reinforce good behavior at school.	3.61	VW
3. inform parents about the policies regarding the use of mobile phones at school.	3.55	VW
4. inform parents about social media networks and their correct use (e.g. Facebook, Twitter, Instagram).	3.56	VW
5. send home Teacher-to-Parent Communication letters or newsletters regarding positive and negative aspects of their children's behavior.	3.57	VW
Composite Mean	3.56	Very Well-Managed

Table 3.2 presents the level of classroom management in terms of parents' collaboration. The composite mean of 3.56, interpreted as Very Well-Managed, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong practices in engaging parents and maintaining effective home-school communication.

All indicators were rated within the Very Well-Managed range, reflecting consistent efforts to involve parents in supporting students' behavior and learning. The highest mean was obtained in teaching parents activities to reinforce good behavior at home, suggesting that teachers actively extend learning and discipline practices beyond the classroom setting.

In contrast, the lowest mean, though still very well-managed, was observed in collaborating with parents on assignments and behavioral plans. This implies that while communication with parents is strong, there is relatively less emphasis on joint planning and shared decision-making in addressing student needs.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers effectively establish collaborative relationships with parents, which contribute to consistent student behavior and improved learning outcomes. Strengthening collaborative planning practices may further enhance the effectiveness of home-school partnerships. This finding is consistent with Callorina et al. (2024), who emphasized that strong parent-teacher collaboration supports student

achievement, reinforces positive behavior, and promotes shared responsibility between home and school.

Table 3.3
Level of Classroom Management in terms of Organization of the Lesson
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. take into account different learning styles when preparing the lesson.	3.47	VW
2. take into account students' previous knowledge to plan the activities based on their level.	3.57	VW
3. establish routines for group work when needed.	3.51	VW
4. start the lesson by giving students an opportunity to set their own learning goals.	3.43	VW
5. make sure that the learning goals are clearly stated for students to understand them.	3.57	VW
Composite Mean	3.51	Very Well-Managed

Table 3.3 presents the level of classroom management in terms of organization of the lesson. The composite mean of 3.51, interpreted as Very Well-Managed, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong competence in planning, structuring, and delivering lessons effectively.

All indicators were rated within the Very Well-Managed range, reflecting consistent use of organized and student-responsive instructional practices. The highest means were obtained in considering students' prior knowledge and clearly stating learning goals, suggesting that teachers effectively scaffold instruction and ensure clarity of expectations, which supports student understanding and engagement.

On the other hand, the lowest mean, though still very well-managed, was observed in allowing students to set their own learning goals. This implies that while teachers maintain strong control over lesson structure, there is relatively less emphasis on promoting student autonomy in the planning phase of instruction.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers exhibit high proficiency in lesson organization, contributing to efficient instructional delivery and improved learning outcomes. Enhancing opportunities for student participation in goal-setting may further strengthen learner engagement and motivation. This finding is consistent with Obispo et al. (2021), who emphasized that effective lesson organization through clear objectives, structured planning, and alignment with learners' prior knowledge enhances classroom efficiency, student engagement, and academic achievement.

Table 3.4
Level of Classroom Management in terms of Interaction During the Lesson
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. start the lesson in an unusual manner to catch students' attention (e.g. telling an amazing story or personal anecdote, starting in a very quiet or low voice).	3.58	VW
2. model the task to demonstrate what students are expected to do (e.g. role playing the task with a student, assigning a student to demonstrate the task).	3.58	VW
3. use concept check questions to make sure instructions are understood (e.g. "what do you have to do first", do you have to work in pairs or in groups?).	3.59	VW
4. use body language to make instructions understandable.	3.55	VW
5. keep English simple and clear (e.g. trying to pronounce every word well, using appropriate pacing according to students' English level).	3.59	VW
Composite Mean	3.58	Very Well-Managed

Table 3.4 presents the level of classroom management in terms of interaction during the lesson. The composite mean of 3.58, interpreted as Very Well-Managed, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong competence in facilitating effective and engaging classroom interactions.

All indicators were rated within the Very Well-Managed range, reflecting consistent use of interactive and learner-centered teaching strategies. The highest means were obtained in using concept check questions and maintaining simple and clear language, suggesting that teachers prioritize clarity of instruction and ensure that learners understand the given tasks. These practices support active participation and improve comprehension during the lesson.

On the other hand, the lowest mean, though still very well-managed, was observed in the use of body language to support instruction. This implies that while teachers are effective in verbal communication, there is relatively less emphasis on maximizing non-verbal cues to enhance understanding, particularly for diverse learners.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers exhibit high proficiency in managing classroom interaction through clear communication, modeling, and engagement strategies. These practices contribute to improved student participation, comprehension, and overall classroom effectiveness. Strengthening the use of multimodal communication, including body language, may further enhance instructional delivery. This finding is consistent with Gabriz and Mackie (2023), who emphasized that effective classroom interaction through clear communication, engagement strategies, and instructional verification enhances student understanding, participation, and motivation.

Table 3.5
Level of Classroom Management in terms of
Teacher-Student Personal Communication
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. attempt to be “Me” rather than “the Teacher” to make students feel I am approachable.	3.59	VW
2. learn students’ names to recognize them as individuals.	3.68	VW
3. interact with students as individuals.	3.62	VW
4. use eye contact to make students feel I care about what they say and do.	3.60	VW
5. learn about the different types of students’ personal and social needs (e.g. using “getting to know each other activities” questionnaires).	3.61	VW
Composite Mean	3.62	Very Well-Managed

Table 3.5 presents the level of classroom management in terms of teacher-student personal communication. The composite mean of 3.62, interpreted as Very Well-Managed, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong competence in establishing positive and individualized communication with learners.

All indicators were rated within the Very Well-Managed range, reflecting consistent use of interpersonal strategies that support student engagement and connection. The highest mean was obtained in learning students’ names, suggesting that teachers emphasize recognition of learners as individuals, which fosters a sense of belonging and strengthens classroom relationships.

On the other hand, the lowest mean, though still very well-managed, was observed in being approachable by presenting oneself as “me” rather than “the teacher.” This implies that while teachers maintain positive communication practices, there is relatively less emphasis on expressing personal authenticity to further enhance openness and rapport.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers exhibit high proficiency in teacher-student communication, which contributes to trust, engagement, and a supportive classroom climate. Strengthening approaches that promote deeper personal connection may further enhance students’ participation and emotional security. This finding is consistent with Ozen and Yıldırım (2020), who emphasized that effective teacher-student communication fosters trust, improves student behavior, and enhances academic engagement through meaningful and individualized interactions.

Table 3.6
Level of Classroom Management in terms of Psychology
n=350

Statements	WM	DI
<i>As a teacher, I...</i>		
1. begin the lesson with activities to reinforce a sense of collaboration among students.	3.52	VW
2. encourage students to be respectful to one another.	3.44	VW
3. promote positive social values (e.g helping, sharing, being patient).	3.44	VW
4. encourage students to reach an agreement through conversations to resolve any issue.	3.25	VW
5. teach students to work together cooperatively toward academic goals.	3.58	VW
Composite Mean	3.44	Very Well-Managed

Table 3.6 presents the level of classroom management in terms of the psychological aspect. The composite mean of 3.44, interpreted as Very Well-Managed, indicates that teachers demonstrate strong competence in fostering a supportive and collaborative classroom environment.

All indicators were rated within the Very Well-Managed range, reflecting consistent use of strategies that promote respect, cooperation, and positive social values among learners. The highest mean was obtained in teaching students to work together cooperatively toward academic goals, suggesting that teachers effectively promote teamwork and shared responsibility in learning.

In contrast, the lowest mean, though still very well managed, was observed when encouraging students to resolve issues through conversation. This implies that while teachers support positive interactions, there is relatively less emphasis on developing students' dialogic and conflict resolution skills.

Overall, the findings indicate that teachers demonstrate high proficiency in managing the classroom psychological climate, thereby fostering positive relationships, student engagement, and a conducive learning environment. Strengthening strategies that enhance peer mediation and communication may further support students' social and emotional development. This finding is consistent with Nkem and Osuafor (2021), who emphasized that psychologically supportive classroom management fosters cooperation, emotional development, and improved academic engagement through structured and positive social interactions.

Table 4.1
Significant Association between the Profile of the Teacher-Respondents and the
Level of Their Socio-Emotional
Learning Competence
n=350

Predictors	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Sex	.01	.04	.02	.28	.78	No significant association
Age	.01	.02	.06	.89	.37	No significant association
Position	-.01	.01	-.06	-1.04	.30	No significant association
HEA	-.00	.02	-.01	-.10	.92	No significant association
Experience	-.03	.02	-.10	-1.39	.16	No significant association

Table 4.1 presents the analysis of the significant association between the profile of the teacher-respondents and their level of socio-emotional learning competence. The results show that all profile variables, sex, age, position, highest educational attainment, and teaching experience, have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating no statistically significant association with socio-emotional learning competence.

This finding implies that teachers' socio-emotional competence does not vary significantly across demographic characteristics. Regardless of differences in sex, age, rank, educational attainment, or years of experience, teachers demonstrate relatively comparable levels of socio-emotional skills.

The acceptance of the null hypothesis suggests that socio-emotional learning competence is not dependent on personal or professional profile variables but may instead be influenced by shared training, school context, or individual professional practices. This highlights the importance of providing inclusive and continuous professional development programs that enhance socio-emotional competencies across all teacher groups. This finding is consistent with Khalid and Raqeeb (2023), who emphasized that teachers' socio-emotional competence is not significantly determined by demographic factors but is more strongly shaped by training, school environment, and professional experiences, underscoring the need for systematic capacity-building initiatives in education.

Table 4.2
Significant Association Between the Profile of the Teacher-Respondents and the
Level of Their Classroom Management
n=350

Predictors	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Interpretation
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Sex	-.00	.03	-.01	-.09	.94	No significant association
Age	.01	.01	.06	.89	.37	No significant association
Position	-.01	.01	-.07	-1.15	.31	No significant association
HEA	-.02	.01	-.08	-1.34	.17	No significant association
Experience	-.01	.02	-.04	-.51	.22	No significant association

Table 4.2 presents the analysis of the significant association between the profile of the teacher-respondents and their level of classroom management. The results reveal that all profile variables, sex, age, position, highest educational attainment, and teaching experience, have p-values greater than 0.05, indicating no statistically significant association with classroom management.

This result implies that classroom management practices are not significantly influenced by teachers' demographic or professional profiles. Regardless of differences in personal and professional characteristics, teachers demonstrate relatively comparable levels of classroom management competence.

The acceptance of the null hypothesis suggests that classroom management skills are developed through professional training, teaching practices, and school-related experiences rather than inherent demographic factors. This highlights the importance of continuous, inclusive professional development programs that enhance classroom management competencies for all teachers. This finding is supported by Ignacio (2024), who reported that teachers' demographic characteristics are not significantly related to their classroom management practices, emphasizing the role of pedagogical training. Similarly, Oliveira et al. (2021) and Huck et al. (2023) found that classroom management effectiveness is shaped more by professional experience and contextual factors than by personal profile variables.

Table 5
Significant Relationship Between the Level of Teachers' Socio-Emotional Learning Competence and the Level of Their Classroom Management
n=350

Source of relationship	Mean	Std. Deviation	Comp r value	Comp p value	Critical p value	interpretation
Socio-Emotional Learning	3.5123	.22605	0.264**	0.00	0.05	There is significant relationship
Classroom Management	3.5479	.16191				

Table 5 presents the significant relationship between teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and their classroom management. The results show that socio-emotional learning competence obtained a mean of 3.5123, while classroom management had a slightly higher mean of 3.5479, both indicating high levels of competence.

The computed correlation coefficient ($r = 0.264$) indicates a positive relationship between the two variables. The computed p-value ($p = 0.00$) is lower than the critical value of 0.05, confirming that the relationship is statistically significant. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected.

This finding implies that teachers with higher socio-emotional learning competence tend to demonstrate better classroom management practices. Although the relationship is moderate, it suggests that socio-emotional competencies such as emotional regulation, social awareness, and interpersonal skills contribute meaningfully to effective classroom management.

Overall, the results highlight the importance of integrating socio-emotional learning in teacher development, as it supports improved classroom practices and learning environments. This finding is consistent with Tao et al. (2022), who reported that teachers' socio-emotional competencies are significantly associated with improved classroom management practices and student engagement. Similarly, McManus (2022) emphasized that teachers with higher socio-emotional competence demonstrate more effective classroom control, stronger relationships with students, and reduced classroom-related stress.

DISCUSSION

This study examined teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management practices in elementary schools across the BiBaCaSiPi districts (Bilar, Batuan, Carmen, Sierra-Bullones, and Pilar) in the Bohol Division during the 2025-2026 school year. It also profiled the teacher-respondents based on key demographic characteristics. The investigation assessed the levels of teachers' socio-emotional

learning competence across core dimensions. Additionally, the study evaluated classroom management. Ultimately, it tested for a significant association between teacher profile and the relationship between socio-emotional competence and classroom management to determine whether to accept or reject the relevant hypotheses.

Findings

The following findings were drawn from the analysis of the data:

1. Profile of the Teacher-Respondents. The teacher-respondents are predominantly female, with most belonging to the 41–50 age group, indicating a mature and mid-career workforce. The majority hold the position of Teacher III, have units in a master's degree, and possess 10 years or less of teaching experience. This profile reflects a professionally active group engaged in career advancement.

2. Level of Socio-Emotional Learning Competence. Teachers demonstrated a Highly Competent level across all dimensions of socio-emotional learning, namely self-awareness, emotional regulation, social awareness, relationship skills, and decision-making. Among these, relationship skills obtained the highest level, while self-awareness registered the lowest, though still within the highly competent range.

3. Level of Classroom Management. Teachers exhibited a Very Well-Managed level of classroom management across all dimensions, including discipline, parents' collaboration, lesson organization, interaction during the lesson, teacher-student communication, and psychological aspect. Teacher-student communication recorded the highest level, while the psychological aspect showed the lowest, though still very well-managed.

4. Significant Association Between Profile and Socio-Emotional Learning Competence. There is no significant association between the profile of the teacher-respondents (sex, age, position, highest educational attainment, and teaching experience) and their level of socio-emotional learning competence.

5. Significant Association Between Profile and Classroom Management. There is no significant association between the profile of the teacher-respondents and their level of classroom management.

6. Significant Relationship Between Socio-Emotional Learning Competence and Classroom Management. There is a significant positive relationship between teachers' socio-emotional learning competence and their level of classroom management, indicating that higher socio-emotional competence is associated with better classroom management practices.

Conclusions

This study concludes that the teacher-respondents generally reflect the profile of public elementary school teachers, characterized by a predominantly female, mid-career workforce occupying Teacher III positions, with ongoing graduate studies and developing teaching experience. The findings further establish that teachers demonstrate high levels of socio-emotional learning competence across all dimensions, particularly in relationship skills, while self-awareness, although still highly competent, presents a relatively lower area that may benefit from further enhancement. In terms of classroom management, teachers exhibit very well-managed practices, with strong emphasis on teacher-student communication, while the psychological aspect, though still highly rated, indicates an area for continued improvement. Moreover, the study confirms that teachers' demographic profile does not significantly influence their socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management. This implies that these competencies are not determined by personal or professional characteristics but are more likely to be developed through training, experience, and professional practice. Finally, the study establishes a significant positive relationship between socio-emotional learning competence and classroom management. This indicates that teachers with higher socio-emotional competence are more effective at managing their classrooms, fostering positive learning environments, and promoting student engagement. Overall, the findings highlight the importance of strengthening teachers' socio-emotional learning as a key factor in enhancing classroom management and improving educational outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Teachers are encouraged to participate in continuous professional development programs that strengthen self-awareness and psychological support strategies to further enhance socio-emotional competence and classroom management practices.
2. Learners may be guided to actively engage in positive interactions with teachers, as mutual trust and communication contribute to a more supportive and effective learning environment.
3. School Heads may prioritize the implementation of school-based socio-emotional learning (SEL) programs and provide opportunities for teachers to apply these competencies through job-embedded training and mentoring.
4. Department of Education (DepEd) Officials may develop and institutionalize comprehensive SEL training programs integrated into teacher development initiatives, regardless of demographic characteristics, to further improve classroom management outcomes.

5. Parents are encouraged to strengthen collaboration with teachers through consistent communication and involvement in school activities to support students' behavioral and emotional development.
6. Future Researchers may conduct further studies focusing on intervention-based approaches and longitudinal designs to examine the impact of socio-emotional learning on classroom management and related educational outcomes.

PROPOSED ACTION PLAN

Rationale

This action plan starts by celebrating what BiBaCaSiPi teachers already do brilliantly: forging real connections with students through those heartfelt personal chats and keeping classrooms humming with smooth discipline and organization. The study shows they're "Highly Competent" in most CASEL areas like relationship skills, but self-awareness lags a bit, and psychological support needs a nudge to match their "Very Well-Managed" strengths elsewhere. Rather than starting from scratch, the 6-month program meets them in their daily routines with job-embedded tools—no travel, no extra load, focusing laser-sharp on emotional insight to turn good into great empathy. The Spearman correlation from the study seals the deal: teachers' socio-emotional strengths like self-awareness and emotional control directly fuel better classroom magic, from fewer disruptions to stronger student bonds and proactive fixes before issues blow up. Weekly reflective sessions help teachers pause and unpack their own triggers—like "Why did that student interaction rattle me?"—while peer coaching lets them role-play real scenarios, such as supporting a kid during an emotional meltdown. CASEL-aligned modules deliver quick, practical strategies that are independent of age or experience, demonstrating that these skills grow through practice, not background, so every mid-career Teacher III walks away empowered.

Picture the payoff: classrooms where empathy isn't occasional but woven in daily, boosting kids' trust during check-ins, easing parents' home reinforcement, and giving school heads ready models for leadership. This builds on research linking SEL to reduced stress, better engagement, and lasting academic gains, creating ripple effects across BiBaCaSiPi districts without overhauling what already works. It's targeted, measurable growth that honors teachers' frontline wisdom while closing the exact gaps the data highlights.

DepEd Order No. 71 s. 2009 laid the groundwork for socio-emotional learning right in the heart of elementary education through Edukasyong Pagpapakatao, zeroing in on the exact skills this study highlights—self-awareness to help teachers recognize their own emotions, and relationship-building to foster the strong student connections we see shining in BiBaCaSiPi classrooms. This policy wasn't just talk; it mandated the integration of core SEL competencies, such as emotional regulation and social awareness, into daily character education, directly supporting the need to boost teachers' emotional insight

without relying on demographics. Fast forward to DepEd Order No. 10 s. 2024 with the MATATAG Curriculum, which doubles down by demanding "emotional smarts" as essential 21st-century skills for real academic breakthroughs, ensuring SEL isn't optional but baked into learning outcomes. Memorandum No. 002 s. 2025 and DM 1215 s. 2025: take it further by embedding SEL directly into teacher training sessions and leadership development, clearing the path for a district-wide rollout in places like BiBaCaSiPi with zero bureaucratic hurdles just straightforward compliance that matches the study's call for targeted growth.

Action Plan Description

This 6-month action plan puts professional growth right in teachers' daily work, no need for off-site workshops that pull them from classrooms. It zeroes in on self-awareness and psychological support—exactly where the study spotted room to grow—while playing to their natural strengths in relationship building and student chats that already create trust. Weekly reflective sessions let teachers pause and check their own emotions, peer coaching pairs them up to practice real scenarios like handling a tough student meltdown, and CASEL modules deliver bite-sized tools for emotional insight. The program builds directly on research showing socio-emotional strengths predict classroom magic: better emotional regulation means fewer disruptions, stronger social awareness sparks proactive fixes, and solid relationships keep interactions flowing. By layering these on teachers' "Very Well-Managed" baseline, it closes the psychological support gap without overhauling what works.

Action Plan Objectives

- Enhance teachers' self-awareness competencies by 25% through reflective practices within 3 months.
- Strengthen psychological support delivery in classrooms, reducing identified gaps via monthly skill-building workshops.
- Integrate SEL into daily routines across BiBaCaSiPi districts, amplifying proactive management strategies for sustained discipline and student interactions.

Mechanics of Implementation

Upon approval from the members of the examining tribunal, the researcher will arrange a presentation to the Public Schools District Supervisor in Carmen 1 district, to discuss the purpose and operational details of the action plan. This meeting aims to foster further collaboration and encourage the active participation of all individuals involved. The researcher is open to accepting their valuable suggestions and recommendations to ensure the meaningful and timely implementation of the intervention plan.

Schedule of Implementation

The action plan is designed as a recurring cycle that spans throughout the year. It is scheduled to commence in January 2026 and conclude in December 2026,

encompassing a range of activities outlined in different categories. After each implementation phase, a thorough assessment and review will be conducted. The purpose of this evaluation is to utilize the monitoring findings as a roadmap for enhancing any areas that require improvement. By actively addressing these areas, the action plan can continuously evolve and strive for greater effectiveness.

Monitoring and Evaluation System

A monitoring and evaluation tool will be created and devised to measure the outcomes of the action plan. This tool will serve as a means to assess the program's progress and identify areas for refinement, as deemed necessary. Regular assessments will be conducted to gauge the effectiveness of the program and ensure its continual improvement.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher ensured that all ethical standards were strictly observed throughout the conduct of the study. Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the appropriate authorities, including the school heads and the Schools Division Office. Participation of the respondents was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was secured before the administration of the survey questionnaire. Respondents were properly informed about the purpose of the study, the nature of their participation, and their right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained by ensuring that no identifying information was disclosed, and all responses were treated with utmost privacy. The data collected were used solely for academic and research purposes and were handled with integrity and responsibility. The researcher also ensured that the study posed no harm to the participants and adhered to the ethical principles of respect, beneficence, and justice throughout the research process.

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